

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B365
Date: 08 May 2008
Take Off: 08:26:47Z
Landing: 12:29:57Z
Flight Time 4h 03

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: Oberpfaffenhofen – Melpitz – Rostock-Laage

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Claire McConnell	University of Reading	
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester	
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester	
12	PAN / Core Chem	Alan Wooley	FAAM	
13	Mission Scientist 2	Keith Bower	University of Manchester	

Flight Track:

B365 Track 08-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B365
 Date: 08 May 2008
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: Eastern Germany - Poland - Baltic Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
063645		Start-Up	1.7 kft	359	8'04.68N, 11'17.51E
080821		ASP	1.7 kft	359	Open Air Sample Pipes
081155	081442	Pirouette 1	1.7 kft	359	start 040deg ,left
082647		T/O	2.5 kft	359	Oberpfaffenhofen
083346		Waypoint	6.9 kft	359	A9
083449		Event	6.8 kft	359	Zero JW & Nevz
083907		Video	6.9 kft	359	Start FFC & DFC
084052	084418	Profile 1	6.8 - 3.7 kft	359	7k'-3.8k', QNH 1019hPa
084418	085554	Run 1.1	3.7 kft	359	3.8k'
084838		Waypoint	3.7 kft	359	Abeam A10
085555	085701	Profile 2	3.7 - 4.6 kft	359	3.8k'-4.7k'
085707	090408	Run 2.1	4.6 kft	359	4.7k', QNH 1020hPa
090256		Waypoint	4.5 kft	359	A54
090408	090552	Profile 3	4.6 - 3.5 kft	359	4.7k'-3.7k'
090552	093642	Run 3	3.5 kft	359	3.7k'
092148		Waypoint	3.5 kft	359	A53
093642	093814	Profile 4	3.5 - 2.2 kft	359	3.7k'-2.3k'
093814	094656	Run 4	2.2 - 2.1 kft	359	2.3k'
093747		Waypoint	2.2 kft	359	A52
094342		Waypoint	2.1 kft	359	Abeam Melpitz
094657	095119	Profile 5.1	2.1 - 7.8 kft	359	2.3k'-8k'
095119	095549	Profile 5.2	7.8 - 2.5 kft	359	8k'-2.7k'
095348		Waypoint	5.0 kft	359	F11
095549	103237	Run 5	2.5 kft	359	2.7k'
095829		Event	2.6 kft	359	Industrial plumes
100925		Waypoint	2.5 kft	359	F13
101502		Waypoint	2.6 kft	359	F14
101756		Event	2.5 kft	359	Heimann Cal
101834		Video	2.5 kft	359	Change tapes
103237	103705	Profile 6	2.5 - 9.0 kft	359	From 2.7k'
104012	105113	Profile 6	9.0 - 26.0 kft	359	Into airway
105432		Event	26.0 kft	359	Zero JW & Nevz
112239	113912	Profile 7	10.2 - -.19 kft	359	1000fpm to 50'
113912	114019	Profile 8	-.19 - 0.26 kft	359	50'-500', Q1021
114019	115345	Run 6	0.26 - 0.27 kft	359	500'
114652			0.30 kft	359	A43
114921		Event	0.29 kft	359	Heimann Cal
114943		Video	0.28 kft	359	Change Tapes
115345	115520	Profile 9	0.27 - 2.0 kft	359	0.5k'-2.2k'
115520	121725	Run 7	2.0 kft	359	2.2k'
115807		Waypoint	2.0 kft	359	A44
120132		Waypoint	2.0 kft	359	A45
120516		Event	2.0 kft	359	D6
120949		Update	2.0 kft	359	Q1020
121725	121924	Profile 10	2.0 - 4.3 kft	359	2.2k'-4.5k'
122957		Land	-.06 kft	359	Rostock-Laage
123622		ASP	-.06 kft	359	Close
123737		Shutdown	-.06 kft	359	53'54.88N, 12'17.33E

B365 Track 08-MAY-08

1. Pilot 1 Alan Roberts (DFL)
2. Pilot 2 Ian Ramsay-Rae (DFL)
3. CCM Dawn Quinn (DFL)
4. Core Chemistry - (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager - (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics – (FAAM)
7. SWS – Debbie O’Sullivan (MO)
8. CPI rack – Dantong Liu (Manchester)
9. wet nephelometer/filters – James Bowles (MO)
10. AMS Rack – William Morgan (Manchester)
11. CCN – Jamie Trembath/Steve Cowan (FAAM)
12. Mission Scientist – Hugh Coe (Manchester)
13. Mission Scientist – Megan Northway (Reading)

Other Comments:

Power on at: 0400Z
Landing Rostock-Laage: 1240Z

Operating Area: Eastern Germany, Poland, Baltic Sea, and northern Germany

Sortie Objectives: To survey eastern Europe and the Baltic during relatively clean conditions in advance of aged pollution predicted to arrive in the region during Saturday. Some local sources are to be expected and it is hoped that we can identify these.

Weather. Atlantic low positioned west of Ireland (1004 mbar) is filling and High off Norwegian coast (1023 mbar), extending over most of central Europe. Occluded front over Irish Sea North-South weakening and stationary. Anticyclonic flow northerly in Baltic, slack to easterly over Central Europe and SE over the North Sea. Light winds, expect close to front over UK.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off EDMO at 08z (10 am local)
3. Profile descent from 5000' to MPA and follow the route:
A9 (EDMO)-A10-A54-A53-A52-A51/F10 (MELPITZ)-F11-F12-F13-F14-F15 along SLR at MPA
between waypoints. Possible sawtooth profiles along route, locations to be determined during flight
[2 hr 15 min]
4. Profile ascent from F15 towards A41, entering upper level airways for transfer between these points.
Use science speed if cloud, else max speed transit (flight levels variable between FL220 and FL260)
5. Profile descent to arrive at A41 at 50 ft at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and 500ft per minute below
3000ft.
[1 hr 15 min, T=3hr 30 min]
6. Profile ascent to maximum of aerosol layer and follow the follow A41-A42-A43-A44 over Baltic Sea
7. Profile ascend from level to MSA over land and follow A44-A45-A46/D6. Head towards D5.
[1 hr, T=4 hr 30 min]
8. End run en route to D5, ascend for approach to Rostock-Laage.
[10 mins, T=4 hr 40 min]

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B365 (dual flight with B366)

Date: 8/05/2008

Sortie Objectives:

In-situ sampling of relatively clean air over Poland and the Baltic Sea in advance of polluted air expected to be transported from the north in the following days. Local sources over eastern Germany and Poland are expected to be sampled.

Operating area:

Eastern Germany, Poland, Baltic Sea and Northern Germany. Landing at Rostock Laage. Way points A9-A10-A54-A51/F10(Melpitz)-F11-F12-F13-F14-F15 (Germany/Poland) and A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46/D6 (Baltic Sea and N.Germany).

Weather:

Surface high pressure centred west of the Norwegian coast. Anticyclonic flow over the Baltic, slack to easterly flow over Central Europe, very light winds.

Summary:

A successful flight sampling relatively clean air over eastern Germany and central Poland, and passing over some power stations in this region. The Baltic Sea showed clear air with aerosol in the lowest 500ft over the sea, but in lower concentrations than measured during flights in other more polluted air masses. Increased pollution over land in Northern Germany.

Flight Patterns:

A pirouette was performed on the runway at Oberpfaffenhofen in clear conditions before take-off. After take-off an initial profile descent to 3.7kft showed aerosol below around 5kft, with a few different layers seen in the scattering below this altitude. We then performed a series of runs at varying altitude depending on the terrain below. Run 1.1 at 3.7kft followed this following the way points in southern Germany, and was well within a weak aerosol layer with scattering only at around 20Mm⁻¹. A filter sample was taken as the aircraft headed northwards from way point A10 along the border of Germany with Austria and then Czech Republic. On approaching A53 scattering increased suddenly to 40Mm⁻¹ and ozone dropped sharply. SMPS showed a bimodal size distribution at this point. On turning eastwards at A53 the CCN/CN ratio and scattering increased to around 60Mm⁻¹ and the SMPS showed a bimodal size distribution. Profile 5.1 was performed between A51 and A52 and showed the boundary layer top at around 7.5kft with scattering and aerosol well mixed below this altitude. The sawtooth descent profile (5.2) found cloud at around 5.5kft. During Run 5 at 2.7kft we passed over several power stations which showed increases in NO_x. Just before reaching point F14 the AMS came online (see problems section). After passing F14 in the west of Poland a profile ascent was performed to FL90 to enter upper airways on route to the Baltic Sea. The PSAP was shut off as we passed through cloud at around 6.5kft and 7.8kft.

A quick transit across Poland to the Baltic brought our profile descent from 10kft to 50ft over the Baltic, which showed relatively little aerosol although there was a sharp increase in scattering below 500ft and the PCASP also saw good vertical structure in the aerosol. Run 5 was performed at 500ft heading southwards across the Baltic, where we saw an increase in SO₂ for the first time during the flight, and the AMS was seeing sulphates, nitrates and organics. SP2 saw increased BC by around 1.5 times and the SMPS saw a unimodal size

distribution. Having passed A43 we approached the coast of northern Germany and saw increased aerosol concentrations. Scattering increased massively to 100Mm⁻¹. A profile to higher altitude was required on reaching the coast and scattering dropped sharply at around 700ft. During Run 6 at 2.2kft all instruments saw decreased concentrations as we were most likely above the boundary layer at this altitude. We then remained at this altitude until reaching way point A46/D6, and then performed a profile ascent and descent to land at Rostock-Laage airport in north Germany.

Problems:

Several power losses to the aircraft before the flight meant that AMS was not running for the first hour and 15mins of the flight.

SMPS was not running for the first hour of the flight.

CLM

FILTERS!

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B365** Date **8/5/08** Name **C. MCCONNELL** Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
081203					Pirouette on runway
081442					End Pirouette
082729					T/20
084052	P1				Descent 7200 → 3000 ft.
0845					~5kft neph ↑. A few layers of scat below, mostly well mixed
084618	R1.1	3.7kft.			Scat ~ 20Mm ⁻¹ . Well within ^{overhead}
084838		"			Waypt A10. Skies currently ^{overhead} clear. NOx ~ 3ppb, CO ~ 200ppb, O ₃ ~ 55ppb
0856					Filters on.
085555	P2				Climb due to terrain.
085707	R2.1	4.6kft			
0858					Scattered Cu above
090256					Way pt A54
090608	P3				Prof to 3.7kft. Cu above.
090552	R3	3.7kft			
0916					scat suddenly ↑ > 40Mm ⁻¹ O ₃ ↓ at same time?
0920					SMPS not working.
0920					Scat back to ~30Mm ⁻¹ . SMPS working. Bimodal.
092148					A53
0926					CCN/CN ratio ↑, as turn to E. Also scat ↑.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.365** Date **8/5/08** Name **C. MCCONNELL** Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09 ²⁸ 31					CN following CEN. ALSO SMPS seeing T small particles.
09345					Scat ~ 60MM ⁻¹
093642	P4	2.3kft			Exit plane - all instruments seeing drops.
093840	R4	2.3kft			A52
0939					Filters off.
0943					ASI passed
094657	P5.1				Saw tooth to 8kft.
					7.5kft top R.
					Scat well mixed below this.
095119	P5.2				Saw tooth descent. Cld @ top.
					~ 5.5kft.
095569	R5	2.7kft			
					Power station below. Not much ^{seen by a/c}
095348					F11
0957					Power station. Nox ↑ > 20ppb.
10003					Some burning to L.
100925					F12 F13
1012					AMS Online.
101502					F14
103237	P6				End R5. Prot to FL90
		4.8kft			Cloud. 6.5kft exit cld.
					7.8kft more cld.
103705	P6				Interrupt prot @ FL90
104012	P6				Recommence profile.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B365** Date **8/5/08** Name **C. McCONNELL** Page **3** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112239	P7				10kft → 500ft over Baltic Sea.
					Sea state calm, no white capping.
113912	P8				Prof to 500ft. Saw stragg ↑ in scat @ ~500ft in P7.
114019	R5	500ft			SO ₂ ↑ for 1st time in Alt AMS - sulphates, nitrates and organics. PCASP saw good vert structure SP2 BC ↑ ~1.5x. SMS unimodal. Clear sky above.
114652					A43
1151					Aer concs ↑ towards coast. Scat > 100Mm ⁻¹ .
115345	P9				Climb 2 to 2.2kft. Scat ↓ sharply ~700ft.
115520	R6	2.2kft.			Concs all instruments ↓ (over land) A44.
115807	A				
120132					A445
120516					A46/06
121725	P10				Prof to 5kft
121926	P10				End P10 to avoid clld @ 5kft End Science.

↑ Scat @ ~4kft.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 365

Date: 08 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
	080500 seadas B365.dat 2dc running 2dp running pcasp vref 7.81 sid1 b365-1.srd ffssp running																
	T/O 082647 Heaters on																
	083615 2dp switched off -just noise in clear air																
084052																Start p1	
084200	700		1	3		0	0										
084418																End p1 start run 1.1 fl36	
084500	1100		2	3		0	0										
084700	1100		2	3		0	0										
084900	1100		2	3		0	0										
085500	1100		2	3		0	0									End run 1.1 start p2	
085700	1000		2	3		0	0									End profile 2 start run 2.1 fl45	
090000	1100		2	3		0	0										
090400	1000		2	3		0	0									End run 2.1 start profile 3	
090600	1100		3	3		0	0									End profile 3 start run 3.1 fl35	
091000	1200		3	3		0	0										
091500	1500		3	3		0	0										
092000	1500		3	3		0	0										
092500	1500		4	3		0	0										
093500	750		4	3		0	0										
0936																End run 3.1 start p4	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
			CIP100 End element 64 voltage =

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 365

Date: 08 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
093800	1700		5	3		0	0									End p4 start run 4.1 fl21	
094300	1500		5	3		0	0										
094657																End run 4.1, start profile 5.1	
094800	1030		6	3		0	0									Fl34	
094850	800		6	3		0	0									Fl40	
094941	600		6	3		0	0									Fl50	
095000	30		6	3		0	0									Fl60	
095119	18		6	3		0	0									Fl80	
095222	80		6	3		0	0									Fl70	
095300	916															Fl60	
095346	1700		10	3		0	0									Fl50	
095520	1900		10	5		0	0									Fl30	
095550	1200		10	5		0	0									Fl25 start run 5.1	
100000	1000		11	5		0	0										
100500	1400		11	5		0	0										
101000	750		12	5		0	0										
101500	750		12	3		0	0										
102000	750		12	3		0	0										
102500	1500		13	5		0	0										
103000	800		13	3		0	0										
103500																End run 5 start profile 6 Cloud, pcasp & ffssp responded, not 2dc(?)	
105000	0		299	1		0	0									Fl257	
105500	4		299	1		0	0									Fl260	
110500	10		300	0		0	0									Fl260	
111600	60		300	1		0	0									Fl167	
111720	70		300	1		0	0									Fl150	
111910	175		300	1		0	0									Fl100	
112530	90		302	1		0	0									Fl80 profile 7	
112800	70		302	1		0	0									Fl60	
113100	340		303	3		0	0									Fl40	
113330	340		303	3		0	0									Fl20	
113612	600		303	3		0	0									Fl10	
	3000		303	5		0	0									50ft	
114100	2000		303	5		0	0									Run 5 500ft fl 02	
114500	1000		303	3		0	0										
115000	1400		304	5		0	0										
115345	1800		304	5		0	0									End run 5	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B365 **T/O:** 082647
Date of flight: 08 may 2008 **Land:** 122957

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOGFlight number: **B365**

Date of Flight:

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat =
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =32289 Blocks written = 32289 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 082000 End = 123500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with im: Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 082000 End =123500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start =082000 End = 123500</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B365****Date of Flight:**

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 082000 123500
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

B365_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

06:43:36.98 --- - - - -
06:43:36.99 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:43:36.99 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:43:36.99 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B365
06:43:36.99 --- - - - -
06:43:47.71 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
06:43:51.52 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
06:43:52.08 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
06:44:03.56 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:44:03.65 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:44:03.74 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:44:23.92 SWS - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:44:25.11 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:44:27.92 SWS - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:44:27.94 SWS - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
06:44:29.92 USH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:44:30.89 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:44:33.36 USH - - 75 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 75ms.
06:44:33.36 USH - - - - 75 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 75ms.
06:44:36.04 USH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
06:44:36.04 USH - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
06:44:38.24 LSH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
06:44:42.63 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
06:44:45.37 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
06:44:45.38 LSH - - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
06:44:53.26 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:44:53.27 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:44:53.27 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:44:58.10 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:45:02.47 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:45:02.48 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:45:02.92 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:45:03.44 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:45:03.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:45:07.46 USH - - - - Idling
06:45:07.47 SWS - - - - Idling
06:45:09.37 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:54:50.25 --- - - - -
07:54:50.28 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:54:50.28 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:54:50.28 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B365
07:54:50.28 --- - - - -
07:54:55.85 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:54:59.67 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
07:55:00.22 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:55:08.79 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
07:55:17.41 SWS - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:55:19.24 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:55:19.31 USH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:55:19.33 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:55:19.42 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:55:21.76 LSH - 100 - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:55:23.58 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:55:26.34 SWS - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:55:26.34 SWS - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:55:27.97 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:55:30.70 USH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:55:30.71 USH - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
07:55:32.32 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:55:34.23 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:55:34.24 LSH - - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:55:41.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:55:41.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:55:41.57 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:55:46.13 --- - - - - Reset shutters.

```

07:55:50.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:50.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:50.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:51.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:51.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:57.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:55:59.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:55:59.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:00.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:00.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:00.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:06.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:12.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:12.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:12.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:56:13.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:13.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:56:12.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:00:18.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 10 deg
08:01:10.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
08:04:57.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
08:08:15.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
08:09:16.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** aiming to maintain cooler temp between 8
and 9 degrees for this flight						
08:09:55.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** as insufficient time to reach lower temps
due to delayed power up (due to GPU failure)						
08:11:14.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** performing a 360 degree piroheutte
08:11:30.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of 360
08:11:39.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** sza 47.92
08:11:49.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** saa 113.86
08:12:04.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction start 360 deg turn now
08:12:20.09	---	-	-	-	-	***
08:14:03.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
08:14:45.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of piroheutte
08:15:43.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
08:16:50.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
08:17:06.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** peltiers off for takeoff so temp will rise
08:17:48.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
08:28:10.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler reached 9 deg c at 08.25
08:28:20.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:28:21.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:28:21.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:28:23.05	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
08:28:28.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:28.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:28.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:33.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:33.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:33.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:33.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:28:34.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:28:34.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:34.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:34.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:28:40.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:42.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:42.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:28:43.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:46.58	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:28:51.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:51.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:51.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:28:52.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:52.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:28:58.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:01.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:01.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:01.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:29:02.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

08:29:02.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:29:08.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:35.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** just passed waypoint A
08:36:48.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** (about 5 mins ago)
08:36:52.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
08:40:58.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** profiloe descent
08:41:15.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile 1
08:44:13.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile 1 start of run 1 at 3800 ft
08:45:38.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
08:48:13.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
08:48:30.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning at left a10
08:51:19.22	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:51:24.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:24.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:24.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:25.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:25.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:31.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:34.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:34.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:35.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:35.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:35.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:41.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:09.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:52:09.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:52:09.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:52:09.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:52:12.65	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
08:52:14.31	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:52:16.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:16.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:16.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:20.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:52:29.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:29.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:29.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:30.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:30.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:35.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:44.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:44.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:44.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:52:45.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:45.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:52:51.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:54.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9
08:54:24.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing from 3800 ft to 4800 ft
08:55:57.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction start of climb now
08:57:02.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile 2 start of run 1.2? 4700 ft
08:57:25.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction run 2.1
08:58:27.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
09:02:29.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** t5urning to right
09:02:58.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint A54
09:04:08.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile decent
09:04:15.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** down to 3700 ft
09:05:01.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
09:05:53.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile 3 start of run
09:06:13.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3
09:06:31.35	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:06:34.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:34.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:35.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:35.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:35.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:41.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:44.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:44.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:06:44.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

09:06:45.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:45.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:06:51.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:08:40.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
09:10:43.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
09:10:52.26	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:10:55.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:55.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:55.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:56.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:56.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:02.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:06.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:06.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:07.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:11:07.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:08.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:13.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:11:52.12	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.500
09:11:56.90	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:11:58.51	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.500
09:12:01.67	SWS	174.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 175.000
09:12:08.21	SWS	175.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.500
09:16:46.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
09:21:49.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint a53
09:22:36.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** coler at 8 deg
09:25:08.03	SWS	174.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:25:12.85	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.500
09:30:20.99	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:30:25.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:25.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:25.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:26.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:26.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:31.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:36.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:36.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:36.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:30:36.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:37.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:42.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:21.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
09:35:14.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
09:36:43.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** descent from 3700ft down to 2300ft
09:36:56.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:57.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:57.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:58.86	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
09:37:00.61	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:37:02.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:02.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:02.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:04.54	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:37:07.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:07.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:08.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:08.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:09.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:14.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:28.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint A52
09:37:28.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:28.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:28.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:29.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:29.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:35.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:38:16.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p3 startbofd run
09:38:42.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction end of P 4 atart of run 4
09:38:57.41	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.

09:39:01.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:01.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:01.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:02.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:02.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:08.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:42.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:40:30.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
09:41:35.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 10 deg
09:42:06.68	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
09:42:06.69	SWS	-	-	-	35	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
09:42:08.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:09.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:13.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:13.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:23.50	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:42:28.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:28.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:28.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:28.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:29.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:33.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:33.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:34.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:34.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:34.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:42.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** over Melpitz
09:43:51.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** Waypoint A51
09:44:00.59	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 35ms to 20ms.
09:44:00.59	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 35ms to 20ms.
09:44:02.53	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 20ms.
09:44:05.15	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 40ms.
09:44:08.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:09.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:12.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:13.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:28.32	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 50ms.
09:44:32.40	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
09:44:34.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:35.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:37.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:39.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:43.95	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:44:48.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:48.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:49.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:50.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:50.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:55.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:21.11	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
09:46:23.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:24.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:26.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:27.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:30.09	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:46:34.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:34.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:34.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:35.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:46:35.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:36.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:46:41.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:49.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:46:59.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of sawtooth
09:47:09.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
09:47:27.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** sawtooth profile 5.1 climbing to 8000 ft
09:49:14.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** lots oc loud around
09:49:52.16	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
09:49:53.14	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500

09:49:55.17	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
09:49:56.05	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
09:49:57.54	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
09:50:10.17	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.500
09:50:50.74	SWS	-9.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
09:51:04.64	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.500
09:51:04.94	SWS	-8.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
09:51:05.28	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
09:51:05.62	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
09:51:05.97	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
09:51:06.29	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:51:06.63	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
09:51:11.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of sawtooth
09:51:15.47	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:51:16.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
09:51:17.83	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
09:51:25.49	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
09:51:25.87	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:51:26.22	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
09:51:26.57	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
09:51:26.89	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
09:51:27.24	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
09:51:29.26	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
09:51:41.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 5.2 descending to 3500 ft
09:51:44.85	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
09:51:45.70	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
09:51:56.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
09:52:03.39	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
09:52:41.44	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
09:52:42.35	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
09:52:42.86	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -1.500
09:53:33.05	SWS	-1.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.000
09:53:36.78	SWS	-2.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -2.500
09:53:49.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** F 11
09:55:08.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
09:55:51.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2700 ft
09:56:19.81	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.000
09:56:20.25	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -3.500
09:56:21.17	SWS	-3.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
09:56:22.01	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.500
09:56:22.58	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
09:56:23.05	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
09:56:24.01	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:56:30.39	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:56:35.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:35.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:35.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:35.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:36.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:36.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:41.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:42.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:45.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:45.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:46.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:46.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:46.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:52.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:55.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:55.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:55.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:56.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:56.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:57:02.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:54.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing through intermittent power station plume
10:03:09.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
10:03:28.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
10:07:55.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg

10:09:27.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** F12
10:09:36.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** actually F13
10:15:08.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** Waypoint F14
10:15:13.73	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:15:18.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:18.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:18.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:19.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:20.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:25.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:36.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
10:15:44.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:44.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:44.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:15:45.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:45.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:15:51.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:48.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
10:32:57.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of tun 5
10:33:04.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profike 6
10:33:56.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
10:35:45.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:35:52.03	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
10:35:52.04	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
10:35:54.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:56.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:03.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:05.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:11.95	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
10:36:11.95	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
10:36:15.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:19.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:35.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
10:36:54.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** interrupted profile climb at fl90
10:37:53.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:58.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:02.63	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:38:08.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:08.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:08.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:08.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:09.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:12.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:17.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** recommencing profile
10:41:06.18	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:41:14.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:14.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:14.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:15.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:15.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:19.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:10.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
10:48:47.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
10:54:06.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 6 ended at 10:40:12
10:55:19.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:19.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:19.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:55:22.20	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:55:23.92	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:55:36.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:36.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:36.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:50.27	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:55:53.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:53.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:53.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:54.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:54.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:58.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:56:05.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:05.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:05.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:06.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:06.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:10.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:43.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
11:09:07.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
11:12:24.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
11:12:56.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** starting descent
11:14:19.21	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:14:23.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:23.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:23.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:24.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:24.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:25.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:28.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:34.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:34.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:34.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:35.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:35.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:39.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:44.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:47.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:48.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:12.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** flying over the sea
11:22:40.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
11:25:22.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
11:26:18.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
11:32:15.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 9 deg
11:34:15.75	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 20ms.
11:34:20.25	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
11:34:20.26	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
11:34:25.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:26.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:28.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:29.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:44.87	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:34:49.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:49.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:49.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:50.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:50.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:54.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:02.51	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
11:35:05.11	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
11:35:09.61	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
11:35:13.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:16.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:19.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:22.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:42.82	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:35:47.63	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:35:59.36	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 50ms.
11:36:01.45	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
11:36:03.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:03.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:04.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:04.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:05.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:08.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:10.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:10.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:10.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:11.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:11.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:15.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```

11:36:39.81 --- - - - - *** SWS looking dodgy - appears to be stuck
shut??
11:37:10.27 --- - - - - *** only sws NIR
11:37:41.46 --- - - - - *** start of run at 50ft
11:39:13.52 --- - - - - *** correction start of run now (pressed enter
by accident)
11:39:19.74 --- - - - - *** climbing
11:40:21.30 --- - - - - *** end of p8 start of run
11:40:33.19 --- - - - - *** run 5 at 500 ft
11:52:16.17 --- - - - - *** climbing to 2200 ft
11:52:44.63 --- - - - - *** not climbing yet, approaching coast
11:53:46.42 --- - - - - *** climbing now to 2200ft
11:53:52.25 --- - - - - *** cooler at 7 deg
11:54:47.52 --- - - - - *** cloud below
11:55:03.85 --- - - - - *** hence sws signal has increased
substantially
11:55:22.54 --- - - - - *** end of profile climb atart of run
11:56:17.07 --- - - - - *** sws nir is fine - just very little signal
over sea
12:00:21.66 --- - - - - *** cooler at 9 degrees
12:05:15.57 --- - - - - *** D6
12:05:30.41 --- - - - - *** cooler at 8 deg
12:10:34.00 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
12:10:38.71 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:10:38.73 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:10:38.82 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:10:39.70 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:10:39.95 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:10:43.60 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:10:49.28 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:10:49.33 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:10:49.36 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:10:50.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:10:50.51 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:10:54.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:16:28.30 --- - - - - *** climb to 5000
12:17:26.87 --- - - - - *** ft now
12:18:54.75 --- - - - - *** cooler at 7 deg
12:19:27.76 --- - - - - *** end of pr
12:19:43.75 --- - - - - *** end of profile 10 at 4500 ft
12:19:59.12 --- - - - - *** end of science
12:21:58.68 USH - - - - Idling
12:21:58.69 SWS - - - - Idling
12:21:58.88 LSH - - - - Idling
12:22:01.42 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:22:03.18 SWS -5.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:22:06.50 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:22:06.51 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:22:06.53 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:22:10.21 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
12:22:15.28 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:22:15.33 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:22:15.39 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:22:15.77 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:22:16.25 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:22:16.92 SWS - - - - Idling
12:22:19.99 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:22:20.10 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:22:20.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:22:21.00 SWS - - - - Idling
12:22:21.22 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:22:39.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:27:49.86 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:29:24.73 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:35:15.49 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:36:23.56 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:37:09.48 SWS - - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
12:37:09.50 SWS - - - 40 - NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
12:37:13.09 SWS - - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.

```

12:37:13.10	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:37:16.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:17.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:19.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:19.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:22.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:37:26.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:26.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:26.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:27.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:27.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:31.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:31.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:31.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:31.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:32.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:32.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:35.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:00.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:00.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:00.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:00.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:01.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:04.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:15.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:40:15.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:40:15.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:40:24.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B**....365....

Date08/05/08.....

Operator's name: ...j.bowles.....

Page ...1.... of

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
085530	1					45		slow start up + filters work
085747		4800	12	33	90	15		1.3 at 90%
090400	p3	to 3700	12	34	50	40		
091220		3500	12	24	86	10		1.4 @ 86%
091835		3500	12.5	32	54	40		
092820			12.4	38	85	10		1.4 -1.5 @85%
093440			12.4	33	52	40		
094010		2100	13	45	85	10		peaks@1.6
094800	p		12	40	60	40		starting saw tooth, leave at 85% when achieved.
095630	r	2700	12	38	87	18		1.4@87%
100320		2500	12	37	58	40		
101149		2500	13	32	86	10		1.4 peak @ 86%
101720		2500	13	31	57	40		
102700		2500	13	37	87	10		peaks @ 1.4-1.5 @87%
103600								chiller off climbing for trans 26000ft
112246		to 50ft	13.9	5.7	39.7	45		Chiller back on and ramp to 85% at 10000ft
113800								Maintaining 85% for profile to 50ft and ascent
114019			17.8	38	91	10		Chiller locked up on/off
115030		500ft	18.0	40.9	58	40		
115933		2000ft	17	36	90	10		

Flight:

B365

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B365

Date: 08 May 2008

Instruments

1. All instruments had reduced pre-flight time due to GPU problems
2. INU – not run
3. Digital Video recording – couldn't get RFC picture on Streaming Activator pre-flight. "Connect Error – Channel2 URL CMD Error". Rebooted server box but no change. FFC,UFC and DFC recorded.
4. Fltsumm – recording 359deg for hdg (this is displayed on Header window as Wind Angle).
5. Core Console Aft – outboard keyboard, right-hand rail not operating properly, falling apart?
6. FFC Window – lots of smudges, will require cleaning on return to base.

Instrument Status roundup

Nephs,PSAP, CVI and Filters - Okay

AMS – No measurements at start of flight due to pre-flight problems. Came online at 1013Z

SMPS – Came online at 0920Z

CCN - Okay

PAN/TDLAS/Core Chemistry – CO calcs drifting for first 2 hours of flight

CAPS/SP2/CPI – CAPS not operated, otherwise okay

Cloud Physics – Switched 2DP off (noisy), otherwise okay

SWS – Okay

Aircraft

1. GPU – not able to hold upload pre-flight and repeatedly lost science power. Start instruments after engine start

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Flight B365 10:52:24

Heading 350 deg Speed 373 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 52°30.0'N Long 18°18.0'E Wind 192 ms-1/ 359 deg

Temp -41.83C Dewpoint -42.06C

From 10:29:21 to now

Current values

STATIC PRESSURE	359.07	mb
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-41.84	deg C
DEW POINT	-42.06	deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B365:

Log	Reason
Pre-flighter log	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created – Keith Bower
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log as CVI was only operated on three flights : B376, B377 & B378
PAN	No log available
CCN	CCN operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b365_081030_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b365_082210_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b365_092210_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b365_102210_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b365_112210_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b365_122210_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b365_081026_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b365_082208_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b365_092208_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b365_102208_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b365_112208_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b365_122208_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b365_081023_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b365_082205_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b365_092205_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b365_102205_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b365_112205_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b365_122205_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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